

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE : DGG

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied xUK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author x did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author x did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the reason for citing sources, according to Kate L. Turabian?

- To reassure readers about the facts.
- To help readers extend the body of work.
- To give credit.
- All of the above.**¹

2. What is one sign of a reliable source?

- The source is published by a reputable press.**²
- All sources are reliable.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139.

² Ibid., 42.

- The source is only available online.
 - The year of the source is old.
3. What are the two kinds of feedback?
- Constructive and non-constructive.
 - Advice and data.**³
 - Long and short.
 - Detailed and vague.
4. When a compound word consists of a noun followed by a prepositional phrase of adjective, how is the word made plural?
- The last noun is made plural by adding 's' or 'es'.
 - The word remains in the singular form.
 - The main noun is made plural by adding 's' or 'es'.**⁴
 - Dashes are added between words.
5. What is the purpose of a colon?
- To separate items within a sentence.
 - To end a sentence fragment.
 - To introduce a clause or phrase.**⁵

3. Turabian, 127.

4. Ibid., 303.

5. Ibid., 321.

- To represent options.
6. When can three periods be placed together?
- When a sentence ends in an abbreviation.
- Two periods can never be placed together.
- Between main and subordinate phrases.
- For ellipses.**⁶
7. When omitting a paragraph or more within a block quotation, how does one indicate the omission?
- Use a period and three ellipses.**⁷
- Use three dashes.
- Nothing is required.
- Use three commas.
8. In dissertation research, what does critical analysis of the literature entail?
- Reviewing the literature in detail.
- Defining key concepts from the research question.
- Describing content gaps in prior research.**⁸
- Making the reader aware of what will be studied.

6. Turabian, 325.

7. Ibid., 379.

8. James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 32.

9. Of what importance is the research design section in a dissertation?

- It accesses the performance of variables.
- It describes how the hypothesis will be examined.⁹**
- It states conceptual or theoretical assumption.
- It describes actions taken to collect data.

10. Which of the following is NOT contained in the appendices?

- The information sources for the literature review and methods.¹⁰**
- Informed consent form.
- Participant demographic data collection forms.
- Questionnaires.

9. Sampson, 35.

10. Ibid., 64.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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